

Regulating the Front-line Orbital Energy Level Enables High-Rate Performance for Lithium-Sulfur Containing Polymers Batteries

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Abstract: Sulfur-containing polymers are promising cathode materials for lithium batteries, offering a novel pathway toward high-energy batteries. Moreover, tuning the frontier orbital energy levels of sulfur-containing polymers can accelerate electrochemical reaction kinetics. Herein, an organic cathode material containing selenium is synthesized using a selenium sulfide solid solution via a previously proposed thiol-sulfur click chemistry reaction, which is a rubber-like material with good mechanical properties. According to front-line orbital theory, the introduction of selenium a group VI element like sulfur, leads to sp^3 hybridization and sulfur–Selenium covalent bond formation. Owing to the electronegativity disparity between sulfur and selenium, electrons accumulate near sulfur atoms, creating nucleophilic sites and continuous negative regions that promote Li^+ transport. As a result, the Li^+ diffusion coefficient increases from $9.7 \times 10^{-13} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ S}^{-1}$ to $2.7 \times 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ S}^{-1}$. The bandgap narrows from 4.14 to 3.89 eV, facilitating lithiation process and enhancing electrochemical performance. Among the cathode materials with different selenium content, the fabricated materials exhibit a superior initial capacity of 580 mAh g^{-1} at 0.05 C and well longer cycle stability. This study reveals how doping modulates frontier orbital energy levels can be employed to enhance reaction kinetics, offering insights for improving sulfur containing polymers-lithium batteries performance.

Key Words: Thiol-Sulfur Click Chemistry; Frontier Orbital Theory; Se-doped; Reaction Kinetics; Lithium-Sulfur containing polymers Batteries.

1. Introduction

Organic electrode materials (OEMs) have recently emerged as competitive alternatives to conventional inorganic electrode materials^[1]. Various OEMs exhibit distinct advantages. Conjugated polymers possess excellent electronic conductivity and can prepare high mass loaded electrodes, though their cycling stability remains unsatisfactory. In contrast, quinone-based OEMs offer superior stability and high specific capacities. Representative examples include anthraquinone (AQ, 256 mAh g^{-1})^[2], benzoquinone (BQ, 496 mAh g^{-1})^[3], and phenanthrenequinone (PQ, 256 mAh g^{-1})^[4], as well as

polymeric derivatives of quinones such as poly(2-chloro-3, 5, 6-trisulfide-1, 4-benzoquinone) (PCTB, 343.1 mAh g⁻¹)^[5], poly(benzoquinonyl sulfide) (PHBQS, 388 mAh g⁻¹)^[6], and anthraquinone-phenylamine CMPs (TNAQ, 236 mAh g⁻¹)^[7]. It has been revealed that sulfur-containing OEMs tend to deliver significantly enhanced specific capacities from insight into molecular-level structural engineering. Sulfur-containing polymer (SCP) electrode materials, owing to their relatively high sulfur content, a sustainable, non-metallic element, can not only modulate redox potentials but also provide high energy densities. Furthermore, their unique molecular flexibility, multifunctionality, low cost, and environmental friendliness, along with the ability to accommodate the structural stress arising during redox reactions, make them promising candidates for metal-ion batteries (MIBs), delivering outstanding electrochemical performance^[8].

Prior studies have shown that although SCPs offer multiple advantages^[9-11]. For example, the flexible polymer chains segments can accommodate the structural changes arising from the volumetric expansion/constriction during redox reaction, thereby preventing electrode collapse. SCP-based lithium (SCP-Li) batteries still face two major challenges: the generation of lithium polysulfides (LiPSs), which leads to the shuttle effect; and sluggish reaction kinetics, resulting in non-ideal rate performance. To address the shuttle effect, structural design of SCPs can be employed by exploiting the tunable nature of their molecular frameworks^[12]. Electron-donating functional groups can be introduced at appropriate sites to adsorb LiPSs. In prior study, with acid-doped polyaniline backbones, a reversible transition occurs between protonated and deprotonated quinonoid imine states during charging/discharging processes. The lone pair (L.p) on the deprotonated quinonoid-N can couple with terminal Li on LiPSs, that effectively anchoring LiPSs and suppressing the shuttle effect^[13]. In general, controlling the number of sulfur atoms in the sulfur chains to fewer than six ($-S_x-$, $2 < x \leq 6$) can significantly reduce shuttling^[10, 14]. To accelerate the battery reaction kinetics, heteroatom doping can be introduced to facilitate lithiation reactions^[15]. This not only enhances redox potential but also improves the electronic conductivity of the material, increasing the carrier mobility and thereby delivering superior electrochemical performance. Iodine doping in the conductive polymer polyacetylene (PA) increases the redox potential to 3.95 V (vs. Li/Li⁺), while improving electrical conductivity by approximately ten orders of magnitude^[16]. Similarly, a composite cathode material (MoS₂-NG@S-SH) has been developed by in situ integration of MoS₂-modified N-doped graphene (MoS₂-NG) with an organic sulfide active material (S-SH). This architecture enhances both the density of adsorption sites and catalytic sites, lowers the energy barrier for LiPSs conversion, and thus promotes faster reaction kinetics^[17].

In this work, a thiol-sulfur click chemistry^[18], proposed in prior work, is employed to synthesize SCP with short sulfur-chains by fine-tuning the stoichiometric ratio of the reactants. The method is simple

and easy to operate. First, infinite solid solution of SSe is prepared, and then reacted with 2, 2'-thiodiethanethiol (TDET) under ambient conditions using diethylamine as a catalyst, yielding polydivinylthio-selenide (PDVTSSe). A sp^3 hybridization occurs between S and Se forming both (S–Se) bond and (S–Se)* anti-bond. The incorporation of selenium modulates the density of states of the sulfur sp^3 orbitals, bringing the Fermi level (E_f) closer to the sp^3 orbital center. The highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) shifts upward toward the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO), thereby narrowing the bandgap. Terminal lithium ions with 1s vacant orbitals overlap with the fully occupied sulfur sp^3 orbitals, forming stable Li–S bonds. Density functional theory (DFT) calculations reveal that the bandgap of PDVTHS decreases from 4.14 eV to 3.89 eV in PDVTSSe_{0.325}, making the lithiation reaction thermodynamically more favorable. Galvanostatic intermittent titration technique (GITT) and rate performance tests clearly demonstrate that the introduction of Se increases the Li⁺ diffusion coefficient by an order of magnitude, reaching $2.7 \times 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ S}^{-1}$. Additionally, the material retains a high discharging capacity of 210 mAh g⁻¹ even at a high current rate of 2 C. This study employs frontier orbital energy level engineering to introduce the heteroatom Se, thereby enhancing the reaction kinetics of the battery. Furthermore, Se-doped SCPs are directly synthesized via thiol-sulfur click chemistry, providing a novel strategy for the rational design of organic cathode materials.

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials and Chemicals

Sulfur (S₈, ≥ 99.5 %, *Canrd*), Selenium (Se, *Aladdin*), 2, 2'-thiodiethanethiol (TDET, C₄H₁₀S₃, > 97 % (GC), *Macklin*), CNT paper (*Nanotechlab*), Li-S battery electrolyte (LiTFSI, *Canrd*), Celgard 2500 as the separator (*Canrd*) were purchased and used as received. Methylbenzene (PhMe) carbon, disulfide (CS₂), and diethylamine (Et₂NH) were purchased from *Chemical Reagents Co. Ltd., China*. All the reagents were analytical grade and used as received.

2.2 Synthesis of SeS Solid Solution

Selenium and sulfur powders (commercially available) were ground together at weight ratios of 1: 3, 1: 6, and 1: 15. The mixtures were transferred into 20 mL hydrothermal reactors and heated at 250 °C for 24 h. Upon cooling to room temperature, a series of SeS solid solutions were obtained, and referred to as SeS-3, SeS-6 and SeS-15, respectively.

2.3 Synthesis of PDVTSSe and PDVTHS

The synthesis was carried out in an argon-filled glovebox (H₂O and O₂ < 1 ppm, Mikrouna). SeS and TDET were added to a MePh/CS₂ mixture ($V/V = 1: 1$) at a molar ratio of 5: 1, followed by vigorous stirring until complete dissolution. Subsequently, 5 μL of catalytic Et₂NH was introduced into the

solution, resulting in immediate effervescence of H₂S gas, which subsided within 10 minutes. The resulting solution was promptly injected into CNT paper to prepare the cathode. The rest of the resulting solution was stirred overnight to yield the sulfur-containing polymer PDVTHS as a precipitate. The final product was dried in an oven at 60 °C for subsequent characterization. The synthesis of PDVTHS followed the same procedure as that of PDVTSSe, except using S₈ in place of the SeS solid solution.

2.4 Synthesis of PDVTSSe/PDVTHS Cathode

CNT paper was punched into 12 mm diameter discs and dried in a vacuum oven for 12 h. Subsequently, 20 μL of the PDVTSSe/PDVTHS solution was drop-cast onto the CNT discs (typically containing 0.01 mmol or 2.8 mg of active material). The in-situ solidification of PDVTSSe/PDVTHS proceeded upon slow evaporation of CS₂, leading to gradual precipitation of the SCP within the CNT framework. The resulting cathode exhibited an aerial loading of 2.47 mg cm⁻². All procedures were conducted in an argon-filled glovebox.

2.5 Materials Characterization

The microstructure of the PDVTSSe/PDVTHS cathode was examined using field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM, JSM-6701F, JEOL, Japan). Elemental distribution was analyzed by energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) mapping (Gemini 300, Zeiss). The elemental composition (S and Se) was determined by inductively coupled plasma-optical emission spectrometer (ICP-OES). X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were recorded using a Bruker D8 ADVANCE diffractometer with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.1541$ nm). Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectra were collected in the range of 4,000~600 cm⁻¹ using a Vectors-80 spectrometer (Bruker, Germany). Raman spectra of the SeS solid solution, pure S and, Se powder were measured over the range of 100–600 cm⁻¹ using a HORIBA XploRA Plus Raman spectrometer (China). ST2643 high-resistance meter was used to assess electronic conductivity of a series SeS solid solution powder, S and Se. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS, ESCALAB 250Xi, Thermo Fisher Scientific) was employed to analyze the chemical states of the SeS solid solution, PDVTSSe/PDVTHS polymer and the corresponding cathodes, with calibration based on the C 1s peak at 284.8 eV. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA, Discovery TGA, TA Instruments) was performed from 25 °C to 800 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ under an argon atmosphere.

2.6 Electrochemical Measurements

CR2032-type coin cells were assembled in an argon-filled glovebox. The cathode was paired with a lithium metal anode, with a Celgard 2500 membrane serving as the separator. A total of 20 μL of commercial Li-S electrolyte was added to both sides of the separator. The cells were sealed and

electrochemical measurements were performed. Cyclic voltammetry (CV) was conducted using an electrochemical workstation (CHI760E, Shanghai, China) in the voltage range of 1.6~3.0 V at a scan rate of 0.1~0.5 mV s⁻¹. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was also performed on the same workstation to evaluate changes in charge-transfer resistance (R_{ct}) before and after cycling, over a frequency range of 100 kHz to 0.01 Hz. Galvanostatic charge/discharge (GCD) tests, rate performance, and cycling stability were measured using a battery testing system (CT2001A, LAND, Wuhan, China) within a voltage window of 1.6–3.0 V. GITT tests were performed at a current density of 0.1 C for 10 min and relaxation for 10 min. The specific capacity was calculated based on a theoretical value of 920.3 mA g⁻¹ (1 C rate).

2.7 Calculation Methods

DFT calculations were performed using the ORCA 6.0.1 software package^[19]. Geometry optimizations for both ground and transition states were conducted with hybrid-GGA functional B3LYP and split valence def2-SVP basis set^[20]. Grimme's dispersion correction DFT-D3(BJ) method was applied for optimization. The local minima structures were confirmed by vibrational frequencies with zero imaginary frequency. The Shermo package was used to derive the thermodynamic correction terms for the computed structures^[21]. The 3D structures were visualized with VESTA.

The first principle calculations (periodicity structures) were carried out with the CP2K 2025.1 software package with Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) functional and Grimme's DFT-D3(BJ) van der Waals correction method, during which the DZVP-MOLOPT-SR-GTH basis set and Goedecker-Teter-Hutter (GTH) pseudopotential were employed^[22]. The plane-waves were cut off at 400 Ry. The ESP figures were rendered by means of the VMD visualization program^[23].

3. Results and Discussion

In our previous study^[18], the organic cathode material PDVTHS has been synthesized using thiol-sulfur click chemistry, which has high specific capacity and excellent cycling stability in SCP-Li sulfur batteries. To further enhance the reaction kinetics of the cathode and improve battery performance, selenium (Se) doping is introduced. In this work, three PDVTSSe materials with varying Se content as cathode active materials are prepared. According to the phase diagram, S and Se can form infinite solid solutions. By adjusting the S/Se molar ratio, three solid solutions: SeS-15, SeS-6, and SeS-3, with increasing Se content were synthesized. As shown in Figure 1a), the Se concentration increases the material color deepened, approaching that of pure Se. Figure 1b) presents the electrical conductivity measurements, revealing that pure Se exhibited the highest conductivity, whereas pure S shows the lowest. The electrical conductivity of the SeS solid solutions increase systematically with increasing Se content. Figure 1c) shows X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of SeS-15, SeS-6, SeS-3,

pure S and Se showed distinct peaks at 24° and 24.6° , corresponding to the SeS solid solution phase^[24]. These peaks differed from those of pure S and Se, and the characteristic peaks of S and Se become weaker, confirming the formation of a new solid solution phase with a crystal structure distinct from either pure S or Se. Raman spectra further confirm these findings (Figure 1d)). A new peak appears at approximately 380 cm^{-1} , attributed to the SeS solid solution phase. The peaks observed at 153, 218.3, and 472 cm^{-1} are attributed to symmetric vibrations of S–S bond, and that at 218.3 cm^{-1} corresponding to the deformation of S–S bonds within the SeS solid solution. Additionally, a new peak at 380 cm^{-1} is detected in the SeS solid solution, which is assigned to the vibrational of Se–S bond^[25]. The Se–S bond signal is more intense in SeS-3 than that in SeS-15, indicating a higher degree of Se substitution in samples with greater Se content. This substitution leads to the formation of more Se–S bond. Furthermore, a blue shift of the peaks from 478 to 371 cm^{-1} can be attributed to ring deformation caused by the incorporation of Se atoms into the S_8 ring structure^[26].

Due to S has a higher electronegativity than Se, the formation of the SeS solid solution causes electron transfer along the atomic chain toward the S atoms adjacent to Se–S bonds. This results in an increased electron cloud density around S atoms. Correspondingly, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) reveals a negative shift in the S $2p$ peak. Meanwhile, the Se $3p$ peak exhibits a positive shift, owing to the reduced electron density around Se. As shown in Figure 1e), the fitted S $2p$ and Se $3p$ spectra of the SeS-6 sample display peaks at 164 and 162.8 eV assigned to S $2p$, and peaks at 166.7 and 161.1 eV assigned to Se $3p$ ^[24]. The partial overlap between the S $2p$ and Se $3p$ peaks reflects the interaction between Se and S via Se–S bonding. Compared to the binding energies of S $2p$ in pure S (164.4 and 163.3 eV), the S $2p$ peaks in SeS-6 shift negatively by 0.4 and 0.5 eV, respectively. Similarly, relative to Se $3p$ peaks in pure Se (166.4 and 160.7 eV), those in SeS-6 shift positively by approximately 0.3 eV. These shifts indicate partial reduction of S and partial oxidation of Se within the SeS solid solution, confirming interaction between Se and S atoms.

According to our previously reported thiol–sulfur click chemistry^[18], polydivinylthio-selenide (PDVTSSe) was synthesized via the reaction of 2,2'-thiodiethanethiol (TDET) with SeS solid solutions at room temperature, using diethylamine ((Et)₂NH₂) as the catalyst, as illustrated in Figure S1 in Supplementary Information. The color change during the synthesis could be clearly observed in glass vials. As the Se content increases, the color of the solution gradually deepened, with the SeS-3 sample exhibiting the darkest appearance. The resulting liquid PDVTSSe is quickly drop-cast onto carbon nanotube (CNT) paper (20 μL per piece, 22.48 mg cm^{-2} of mass load). The remaining solution was transferred to a 60°C oven and dried overnight. After solvent evaporation, PDVTSSe formed a brownish rubber-like solid with a certain degree of flexibility. The S and Se contents in different SCP materials are determined by inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES),

and the detailed results are summarized in **Table S1** in Supplementary Information. The synthesized PDVTSSe with various Se content are recorded as PDVTSSe_{0.191}, PDVTSSe_{0.325}, PDVTSSe_{0.776}. In the sample PDVTSSe_{0.191}, the S content was 70.05 %, and the Se content was 4.73 %, corresponding to an atomic ratio of S to Se of approximately 1:0.03. For PDVTSSe_{0.325}, the S and Se contents were 68.66 % and 7.87 %, respectively, with an atomic ratio of 1: 0.05. In PDVTSSe_{0.776}, the S content was 63.22 %, and the Se content increased to 17.3 %, yielding an atomic ratio of 1: 0.11. X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis is performed on PDVTSSe_{0.191}, PDVTSSe_{0.325}, and PDVTSSe_{0.776} with varying selenium contents, and the results are compared with those of non-selenized PDVTHS, as well as with pure S and Se powders (Figure 2a). No characteristic peaks of elemental sulfur were observed in PDVTHS, indicating that sulfur was fully incorporated into the polymer chains through chemical bonding. The broad diffraction peak observed in the low-angle region (10°~20°) is attributed to the scattering of amorphous materials, confirming the polymeric nature of the product. Similarly, the XRD patterns of PDVTSSe_{0.191}, PDVTSSe_{0.325}, and PDVTSSe_{0.776} also exhibit broad shape, featureless diffraction signals without distinct S or Se crystalline peaks, further indicating their amorphous nature and the complete incorporation of S and Se into the polymer backbone. The XPS analysis of survey spectrum on PDVTSSe_{0.325} is shown in Figure 2b), the sample contains C, S and, Se. Figure 2c) delivers the fine spectrum of C 1s, S 2p and, Se 3d. C 1s exhibits a peak at 284.2 eV, which is attributed to C–S bonds. The S 2p spectrum displays two peaks at 164.0 and 162.8 eV, corresponding to the S 2p_{1/2} and S 2p_{3/2} components, respectively. These peaks are associated with S–S, S–Se and, S–C bonds. The fine Se 3d spectrum shows peaks at 55.9 and 55.0 eV, which can be assigned to Se–S bonding. These peaks are positively shifted by 2.7 eV compared to the Se–Se peaks in pure elemental Se (53.2 and 52.3 eV, Figure S2 in Supplementary Information), indicating that Se is chemically bonded to S in the polymer chain and is partially oxidized by the surrounding S atoms^[27].

The XRD pattern of PDVTSSe (Figure 2d)) reveals no crystalline peaks associated with elemental S, Se, or SeS solid solution, suggesting that the reaction proceeded to completion with full conversion into the polymeric product. The only visible peak at 26° originates from the CNT paper substrate, consistent with the XRD pattern of pristine CNT paper (Figure S3 in Supplementary Information). Figure 2e) expresses Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy that further confirms the transformation of the precursor TDET into the PDVTSSe polymer. The S–H characteristic stretching vibration at 2546 cm⁻¹ observed in TDET disappears after polymerization, while a new peak at 833.5 cm⁻¹ emerges, indicating S–S bond formation and successful crosslinking. In addition, the vibrations at 713.5 cm⁻¹ (C–S bond) and 1, 415.5 cm⁻¹ (C–H bond) are significantly weakened compared to those in TDET, which may result from a reduction in molecular freedom upon polymerization. In addition, doping contributes to improved thermal robustness of the material (Figure S4 in Supplementary

Information).

As shown in Figure 2f), the PDVTSSe synthesized via thiol–sulfur electrochemical click chemistry, exhibits a rubber-like texture with inherent mechanical flexibility. A PDVTSSe_{0.325} strip measuring 4 cm in length could be stretched to 6.5 cm and be capable of lifting a 500 g weight with ease, demonstrating its mechanical robustness. To quantitatively evaluate its mechanical properties, Figure 2g) compares the toughness and Young's modulus of samples with varying Se content, including the Se-free PDVTHS. Se incorporation is found to enhance both the stiffness and toughness of the polymer network. The incorporation of Se atoms likely introduces interfacial reinforcement, effectively restricting chain segment mobility and enhancing the bulk mechanical properties. Moreover, Se may modulate the electronic structure or charge distribution, thereby strengthen intermolecular interactions and further improving mechanical robustness^[28-30]. Specifically, the Se-free PDVTHS exhibit a Young's modulus of 282 kPa and a toughness of 0.087 MJ m⁻³, reflecting low rigidity. Upon Se doping, both Young's modulus and toughness increase significantly, PDVTSSe_{0.191} (289 kPa, 0.181 MJ m⁻³), PDVTSSe_{0.325} (513 kPa, 0.489 MJ m⁻³), PDVTSSe_{0.776} (407 kPa, 0.365 MJ m⁻³). Young's modulus reflects a material's resistance to elastic deformation. A higher value indicates greater stiffness. Toughness quantifies the energy a material can absorb before fracturing. In the context of battery electrodes, increased toughness allows the material to accommodate volume changes caused by redox reactions of the active species, helping to prevent cathode structural collapse. Interestingly, both Young's modulus and toughness exhibit a non-monotonic trend with increasing Se content: they first increase and then decrease, reaching their peak values in PDVTSSe_{0.325}. This suggests that moderate Se doping substantially improves mechanical performance, while excessive Se content may compromise the polymer's structural integrity. Therefore, optimizing Se concentration is critical for balancing elasticity and strength in polymer-based cathodes.

Figure 2h) shows the stress-strain curves, both stress and strain values is improved with Se incorporation. For PDVTHS, the tensile stress and strain were 0.142 MPa and 0.937%, respectively. These values increased in PDVTSSe_{0.191} (0.175 MPa, 1.43%) and PDVTSSe_{0.776} (0.38 MPa, 1.43%), reaching the highest levels in PDVTSSe_{0.325} (0.41 MPa, 1.60%). This indicates that PDVTSSe_{0.325} possesses the best tensile performance among the tested samples. To enhance the electrical conductivity of the cathode, active materials with different Se contents is loaded onto CNT paper to fabricate PDVTSSe composite electrodes, hereafter referred to as PDVTSSe_{0.191}, PDVTSSe_{0.325}, and PDVTSSe_{0.776}. The scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of these electrodes are shown in Figure S5 in Supplementary Information. Despite the varying Se content, no significant morphological differences are observed among the three samples. Compared with pristine CNT paper (Figure S6 in Supplementary Information), the SEM images clearly reveal that the polymer coats the CNT network

uniformly. EDS mapping further confirms the homogeneous distribution of C, S, and Se on the electrode surface.

Figure 3 presents the galvanostatic intermittent titration technique (GITT) curves of SCP electrodes with three different selenium contents. All electrodes exhibit similar electrochemical behavior and charging/discharging plateaus. Compared to the PDVTHS cathode, which shows an average voltage plateau of 2.08 V (Figure S7 in Supplementary Information), the average plateau increases to approximately 2.14 V for the Se-containing cathodes. This increase is attributed to the inherent redox potential of S/S²⁻ in the SSe solid solution (0.142 V vs. SHE), which is higher than the redox potential of Se/Se²⁻ in pure selenium (-0.399 V vs. SHE). As shown in Figure 3a-c) the Se content increases, the average polarization voltage between transient curves (solid lines) decreases, indicating reduced electrochemical polarization of the batteries. Additionally, the polarization voltages between the steady-state curves (dashed circles) are 0.185 V, 0.149 V, and 0.14 V for PDVTSSe0.191, PDVTSSe0.325, and PDVTSSe0.776 cathodes, respectively. This reduction in polarization is not only due to improved polymer conductivity from Se doping but also confirms the synergistic effect between S and Se within the SCP. Measurement of the lithium ions diffusion coefficient is a crucial method for investigating electrode kinetics. A higher diffusion coefficient corresponds to better high-current discharge capability, higher power density, and improved rate performance of the electrode material. Inhere, GITT is employed to estimate the lithium-ion diffusion coefficient (D_{Li^+}) within the active material. By analyzing the relationship between the electrode potential changes and the relaxation time, combined with the physicochemical parameters of the active material, the impact of selenium doping in the SCP on the battery reaction kinetics is evaluated. The Li⁺ diffusion coefficient is calculated according to the following equation^[31]:

$$D = \frac{4}{\pi\tau} \left(\frac{m_b V_m}{M_b S} \right)^2 \left(\frac{\Delta E_s}{\Delta E_t} \right)^2$$

where τ is the relaxation time; m_b is the mass of the active material; V_m is the molar volume of the electrode material; M_b is the molar mass of the active material; S is the electrode/electrolyte contact area; ΔE_s is the voltage change caused by the current pulse; and ΔE_t is the voltage change during the constant current charge (discharging).

As demonstrated in Figures 3a-c), the GITT curves of cathodes with different Se contents, exhibiting similar voltage plateaus and electrochemical behaviors. Consistent with previous reports, the high-voltage plateau at a depth of discharge of around 18 % corresponds to the cleavage of C–S bonds in PDVTSSe. These C–S bonds have lower bond energy than S–S and S–Se bonds. During this stage, two Li⁺ ions combine to form LiS₂C₄H₈S₂SeLi, resulting in a faster Li⁺ diffusion rate, reaching up to 10⁻¹⁰ cm² S⁻¹ (Figure 3d and f)) and even 10⁻⁹ cm² S⁻¹ in PDVTSSe0.325 (Figure 3e)). At a depth of

discharge between 18 % and 90 %, the Li^+ diffusion coefficients are significantly improved compared to the PDVTHS cathode (Figure S7 in Supplementary Information), and the diffusion curves are more stable. The values are $5.3 \times 10^{-13} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ S}^{-1}$, $2.7 \times 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ S}^{-1}$, and $7.4 \times 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ S}^{-1}$ for PDVTSSe_{0.191}, PDVTSSe_{0.325}, and PDVTSSe_{0.776} cathodes, respectively. This plateau corresponds to the further discharging of intermediate products to the final discharge products, including 2, 2'-thiobis(lithium eththiolate) ($\text{LiSC}_4\text{H}_8\text{S}_2\text{Li}$), Li_2S , and Li_2Se . During the charging plateau, the Li^+ diffusion coefficient in the PDVTSSe_{0.325} electrode shows a more pronounced increase, reaching $5.0 \times 10^{-11} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ S}^{-1}$ at 60 % state of charge. The charging plateau represents the reversible conversion of discharging products back to the reactant PDVTSSe. The enhanced Li^+ diffusion rate can be attributed partly to the improved electrical conductivity of the active material and partly to the presence of Se, which facilitates electron fast transfer. Consequently, this superior conductivity promotes the easier interconversion between high-order polysulfides, low-order polysulfides, and discharge products.

To investigate the impact of Se doping on the electrode kinetics, cyclic voltammetry (CV) tests are performed on the three cathodes at scan rates ranging from 0.1 to 0.5 mV s^{-1} (Figure 4a-c)). The CV curves maintain consistent shapes across different scan rates, demonstrating excellent electrochemical stability. With increasing Se content, the electrochemical polarization of the electrodes exhibits a trend of initially decreasing followed by increasing illustrated in Figure S8 in Supplementary Information. Among them, the PDVTSSe_{0.325} cathode shows the lowest polarization of 0.37 V. Since larger polarization hinders rapid reaction kinetics, this observation is consistent with the GITT-derived kinetic profiles, where PDVTSSe_{0.325} exhibits the highest Li^+ diffusion coefficient. Further analysis of the oxidation peak A and reduction peaks B and C allowed plotting of peak current (I_p) versus the square root of scan rate ($v^{0.5}$) curves in Figure 4d-f). Although PDVTSSe_{0.776} and PDVTSSe_{0.191} showed larger slopes in reduction peak B, likely due to faster electrochemical conversion at the first plateau, PDVTSSe_{0.325} display the highest slopes for oxidation peak A and reduction peak C. This indicates more complete and faster conversion during battery reactions, contributing to superior reaction kinetics. Additionally, as shown in Figure 4g-i) Tafel slopes derived from the CV data reveal that at full discharging (Peak B) and full charging (peak A), PDVTSSe_{0.325} exhibit the lowest Tafel slope of 0.024 V dec^{-1} , 0.23 V dec^{-1} among the three cathodes, respectively. This suggests faster reaction kinetics during both discharging and charging processes. This performance enhancement can be attributed to the synergistic effect between Se and S, where an optimal Se content accelerates discharge reaction completion and promotes reversible conversion between discharge products and the initial active material.

Understanding the molecular-level orbital changes of cathode materials during battery cycling is essential for elucidating SCP-Li battery performance, stability, and overall lifespan. In this study, the SCP cathodes with and without Se doping are evaluated. Specifically, the initial lithiation processes of three cathodes with different Se contents were analyzed through Gibbs free energy (ΔG) calculations, using dimeric structures to represent the molecular architecture of the SCPs. Due to differences in bond cleavage sites during initial lithiation, the ΔG values vary across different lithiation pathways, which allows for the assessment of lithiation probability based on reaction thermodynamics. A lower Gibbs free energy corresponds to a more spontaneous lithiation reaction^[32]. As shown in Figure S9 in Supplementary Information, PDVTSSe_{0.325} does not exhibit the lowest ΔG among the three cathodes, which thermodynamically explains the electrochemical behaviors observed in Figures 4e and 4h. Those results suggest that PDVTSSe_{0.191} and PDVTSSe_{0.766} undergo faster initial lithiation. Notably, the lithiation pathway of PDVTSSe_{0.325} aligns well with the predicted mechanism, as illustrated in Figure 5a. Lithiation initiates via bond cleavage at site-1, yielding the intermediate LiSSeSC₄H₈S₂SeSLi and two equivalents of Li₂S, with a reaction free energy of $\Delta G = -274$ kcal mol⁻¹. Upon further lithiation, the intermediate transforms into LiSC₄H₈SLi and two equivalents of Li₂Se, with $\Delta G = -173.8$ kcal mol⁻¹. These results corroborate the proposed lithiation mechanism and its thermodynamic feasibility, further highlighting the role of Se in modulating the reaction thermodynamics of SCP cathodes. Compared with the undoped PDVTHS cathode (Figure S10 in Supplementary Information), the Se-doped PDVTSSe_{0.325} shows a lower ΔG for lithiation, indicating a more thermodynamically favorable and spontaneous reaction. This suggests that the Se-doped cathode exhibits a faster redox reaction rate and enhanced Li⁺ transport, that is consistent with the GITT results.

To visualize the charge distribution, electrostatic potential (ESP) analyses are performed on PDVTSSe_{0.325} and PDVTHS. As shown in Figure 5b, in the PDVTSSe_{0.325} molecule, the blue regions indicate electron-deficient areas are primarily localized around the Se atoms, corresponding to regions of positive electrostatic potential. In contrast, the red regions representing electron-rich areas are mainly concentrated near the S atoms, corresponding to more negative potentials and nucleophilic character^[8]. Furthermore, the presence of a continuous negative ESP pathway along the polymer backbone facilitates efficient interchain electron transport. When S and Se form covalent bonds, the higher electronegativity of S causes the electron cloud around Se to shift toward S. Upon cleavage of the S–Se bond, electrons near the Se atom tend to remain around the S atom, increasing the electron density and negative potential at the S site (Figure S11 in Supplementary Information). As shown in Figure 5c, the S–Se bond forms through hybridization between the 3s and 3p orbitals of S and the 4s

and 4*p* orbitals of Se. The introduction of Se alters the molecular orbital energy levels and the band structure of the material. In the simplified model used for band structure analysis (Figure 5d), *sp*³ hybridization between S and Se generates both bonding (S–Se) and antibonding (S–Se)*, clearly indicating electron flow from Se to S. Figure 5e and f) schematic the lithiation process of the active material is fundamentally governed by the orbital overlap between molecules. Specifically, the 1*s* empty orbital of terminal Li interacts with the filled S *sp*³ orbital to form a Li–S bond. Se doping modulates the density of states (DOS) of the S *sp*³ orbital, shifting the Fermi level (*E_f*) closer to the center of the S *sp*³ state. As a result, the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) moves upward and becomes closer to the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO), effectively narrowing the bandgap. Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations confirm these observations: the bandgap of PDVTHS and PDVTSSe_{0.325} are 4.14 eV and 3.89 eV (Figure 5g), respectively. After initial lithiation, the bandgaps of the resulting products LiS₂C₄H₈S₃Li and LiSeSC₄H₈S₂SeLi decrease further to 2.45 eV and 2.41 eV (Figure 5h), respectively. These results demonstrate that Se doping effectively reduces the bandgap, making the lithiation reaction more thermodynamically favorable and leading to more stable lithiation products.

In Figure 6a), the survey spectra clearly indicate the presence of S, Se, and C in all samples. However, peak intensities vary due to differences in their chemical environments. To better understand the redox behavior during charging/discharging, ex-situ XPS analysis of PDVTSSe_{0.325}, pristine PDVTSSe_{0.325} cathode and PDVTSSe_{0.325} cathodes at different states are compared. In Figure 6b), the C 1*s* spectrum of PDVTSSe_{0.325} shows peaks at 284.2 and 284.8 eV, corresponding to C–S and C–C bonds. For PDVTSSe_{0.325} cathode, the C 1*s* peak splits, likely due to changes in the carbon bonding environment. Upon discharge, the C–S peak shifts positively by 0.3 eV, attributed to molecular chain breakage that strengthens C–S bonding. Since sulfur is more electronegative than carbon, this causes a reduction in the electron density around C atoms. Conversely, the C–C peak shifts negatively by 0.3 eV due to electron gain during discharge, which lowers the binding energy. Peaks at 287.3 and 291.8 eV originate from residual electrolyte species on the cathode surface. Figure 6c) shows the fine S 2*p* spectra. The peak at 162.8 eV in PDVTSSe_{0.325} is assigned to Se–S bonds and –SH groups, while the 164.0 eV peak corresponds to S–S and S–C bonds. Compared to the PDVTSSe_{0.325}, these peaks in the PDVTSSe_{0.325} cathode shift positively by 0.5 eV, reflecting changes in the carbon bonding environment upon cathode fabrication. For PDVTSSe_{0.325} cathode, when discharging to 1.6 V, the S 2*p* spectrum shows the emergence of peaks corresponding to S–Li (162.1 eV), LiSC₄H₈S₂Li (163.3 eV), partially reduced lithium polysulfides (Li₂S_{*x*}, 2 ≤ *x* ≤ 4) at 168.1 eV, and a small amount of reaction byproduct sulfonates

(S=O) at 169.4 eV. On the contrary, upon recharging to 2.8 V, the –SH group (162.9 eV) reappears, while the discharging products, lithium polysulfides (LiPSs), are reversibly converted back to PDVTSSe_{0.325}, leading to a decrease in their concentration. The peaks attributed to S–S and S–C bonds also reemerge and shift positively to 168.8 eV due to electron loss during the charging process. Similarly, the Se 3*d* high-resolution spectra^[33] exhibit changes analogous to those of sulfur during cycling (Figure 6d)). When discharged to 1.6 V, peaks at 54.8 and 58.3 eV correspond to Se–S bonds, the other peak at 52.5 eV is assigned to the discharge product Se–Li. Upon recharged to 2.8 V, the Se–Li peak disappears, confirming the reversible redox conversion of PDVTSSe_{0.325}. Figures 6e-h) show the morphology of PDVTSSe_{0.325} cathodes at different states. In the pristine, partially discharged, and recharged cathodes, the sulfur-containing polymer is uniformly coated on the carbon fibers, with both sulfur and selenium elements evenly distributed. In contrast, the fully discharged cathode (1.6 V) reveals clearly distinguishable carbon fibers. These observations further confirm the reversible conversion of the active material PDVTSSe_{0.325} during battery operation.

To evaluate the electrochemical performance of a series of PDVTSSe electrodes with varying Se content, the SCP-Li batteries are assembled using different electrodes paired with lithium metal. The theoretical capacities of the SCP materials are calculated based on the polymer and the respective S&Se contents. Detailed information is provided in Table S2 in Supplementary Information. In Figure 7a), from 0.05 to 2 C rate, all three cathodes exhibit stable electrochemical performance. At a low rate of 0.05 C, the specific capacities reach 504.2, 543.4, and 434 mAh g⁻¹ for PDVTSSe_{0.776}, PDVTSSe_{0.325}, and PDVTSSe_{0.191} cathodes, respectively. As the rate increase, the PDVTSSe_{0.325} cathode demonstrate superior rate capability, delivering capacities of 335 mAh g⁻¹ at 1 C and 210 mAh g⁻¹ at 2 C. In contrast, the PDVTSSe_{0.776} and PDVTSSe_{0.191} cathodes show significantly lower capacities of 208 and 96 mAh g⁻¹, and 154 and 57 mAh g⁻¹ at the same rates. When the current rate was reverted to 0.1 C, the capacities recover well to 369 mAh g⁻¹ (PDVTSSe_{0.776}), 427 mAh g⁻¹ (PDVTSSe_{0.325}), and 380 mAh g⁻¹ (PDVTSSe_{0.191}). Long-term cycling performance at 0.2 C is shown in Figure 7b), where the PDVTSSe_{0.325} cathode initially deliver 410 mAh g⁻¹ and retain 274 mAh g⁻¹ after 220 cycles. Figure 7c-e) present galvanostatic charge-discharge (GCD) curves of the three cathodes at various rates. Compared to PDVTSSe_{0.776} and PDVTSSe_{0.191} cathodes, PDVTSSe_{0.325} exhibit smaller electrochemical polarization and deliver higher capacities at identical rates. Figure 7f) shows the long-term cycling stability of PDVTSSe_{0.325} at 1 C, with an initial capacity of 165 mAh g⁻¹, retaining 117 mAh g⁻¹ after 630 cycles, capacity retention of 71%, demonstrating excellent electrochemical stability. Furthermore, in Figure S12 in Supplementary Information electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements of PDVTSSe_{0.325} cathode show a reduced R_{ct} after 630 times of cycling, indicating that the synergistic interaction between S and Se facilitates faster charge

transfer and promotes the battery reaction.

It is noteworthy that the above electrochemical performance metrics are calculated based on the total polymer mass. Capacities calculated based on the S and Se content are presented in the Supporting Information. Therefore, Figure S13 in Supplementary Information compares the rate performance of the three cathodes based on S&Se, showing capacities of 625, 710, and 580 mAh g⁻¹ at 0.05 C for PDVTSSe_{0.776}, PDVTSSe_{0.325}, and, PDVTSSe_{0.191}, respectively. Figure S14 and S15 in Supplementary Information show the long-term cycling performance of PDVTSSe_{0.325} (initial capacity of 209 mAh g⁻¹) based on S&Se content, and a comparison of capacities for PDVTSSe_{0.776} and PDVTSSe_{0.191} cathodes calculated from polymer mass and S&Se content.

4. Conclusions

In summary, a series of PDVTSSe materials with varying Se contents were synthesized using the previously established thiol–sulfur click chemistry method. Electrochemical and spectroscopic analyses confirmed that PDVTSSe_{0.325} exhibits the best cathodic performance among the synthesized materials. By introducing Se, a group VI element similar to S, S and Se atoms in the PDVTSSe_{0.325} framework undergo *sp*³ hybridization to form S–Se covalent bonds. DFT calculations reveal that this structural modification precisely tunes the HOMO energy level and significantly reduces the HOMO/LUMO bandgap (E_g), facilitating the lithiation process and enhancing reaction kinetics. GITT and rate capability tests demonstrate that Se incorporation increases the Li⁺ diffusion coefficient to 2.7×10^{-12} cm² S⁻¹, an order of magnitude improvement, while also delivering good capacity under high-rate conditions. This study presents a viable strategy of heteroatom (Se) engineering to modulate frontier orbital energies and accelerate battery kinetics, offering a new pathway for the rational design of sulfur-containing conjugated polymers (SCPs).

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Supplemental Information

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Figure 1. a) Optical photography, b) electronic conductivity, c) XRD patterns and d) Raman patterns of various SeS solid solutions. e) High resolution XPS spectra of Se 3p in pure Se, S 2p + Se 3p in SeS and S 2p in pure S.

Figure 2. a) XRD patterns of different SCP samples. b) XPS survey spectrum and c) C 1s, S 2p, Se 3d XPS fine spectrum of PDVTSSe_{0.325}. d) XRD spectra and e) FTIR of different samples. f) Tensile test digital photograph of PDVTSSe_{0.325}. g) Toughness and Young's modulus changes curves. h) Stress-strain curves of different samples.

Figure 3. a-c) GITT curves of the variants with different Se content, and corresponding Li⁺ diffusion coefficients in d) PDVTSSe_{0.191}, e) PDVTSSe_{0.325}, and f) PDVTSSe_{0.776}.

Figure 4. CV curves of a) PDVTSSe_{0.191}, b) PDVTSSe_{0.325}, and c) PDVTSSe_{0.776} at different scan rates; d-e) CV redox peaks current vs the square root of scan rate, g-i) Tafel plots of PDVTSSe_{0.191}, PDVTSSe_{0.325}, and PDVTSSe_{0.776}.

Figure 5. a) The reaction mechanism of PDVTSSe_{0.325} during discharging process and corresponding ΔG . b) Polymer structure and electrostatic potential comparison of PDVTSSe_{0.325} and PDVTHS. As depicted from c) to d) the schematic band structure of S–Se can be built by extrapolating c) the molecular orbital energy diagram of S and Se. The molecular orbital energy diagram during lithiation for e) PDVTSSe and f) PDVTSSe_{0.325}. A comparison of the DFT calculated HOMO/LUMO energy level diagrams of g) PDVTSSe, PDVTSSe_{0.325} and h) single lithiated PDVTHS (LiS₂C₄H₈S₃Li), PDVTSSe_{0.325} (LiSeSC₄H₈S₂SeLi) by frontier molecular orbital analysis.

Figure 6. a) XPS spectra of PDVTSSe_{0.325} cathode at different electrochemical states, along with high-resolution spectra of b) C 1s, c) S 2p, and d) Se 3d. e-h) SEM images and corresponding elemental mappings of the fresh PDVTSSe_{0.325} cathode at various charging/discharging states.

Figure 7. a) Rate properties curves ranging from 0.05 to 2 C, b) cycling performance at 0.2 C and c-e) the corresponding GCD curves for different cathodes; f) Long-term cycling performance of PDVTSSe_{0.325} cathode at 1 C.